

Thallium(I) Complexes of 2-Mercaptoethanol. A Polarographic Study

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The formation, composition and stability constants of Thallium(I) complexes with 2-mercaptoethanol have been studied polarographically, adopting DeFord and Hume's method. The coordination number (N) calculated from the slopes of plot of $-E_{1/2}$ vs. $-\log [\text{ligand}]$ gave two segments showing the existence of 1:1 and 1:2 complex species. The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS of the complexation reaction have also been determined.

ORGANO sulphur compounds containing an active -SH group, are well known for their tendency to form complexes with metals¹⁻³ and have great significance in biological, pharmaceutical and in resin industries. Polarographic behaviour and metal complexes of several such compounds have already been investigated in these laboratories by Saxena *et al.*⁴⁻⁸. In this communication, the formation, composition and stability constants of Tl⁺ complexes with 2-mercapto-ethanol have been studied polarographically.

Experimental

2-mercaptoethanol (referred to herein as RSH) and all other chemicals were Anala R/BDH grade: Fresh solutions were used to avoid the effects of ageing and air-oxidation. All solutions used in polarographic measurements had in addition to RSH, Tl⁺ ion concentration of 0.8 mM, 0.1M KNO₃ and 0.002% Triton X-100 in aqueous media at pH = 4.0. The entire study was carried out in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen.

polarograms against S.C.E. as a reference electrode. The capillary had the following characteristics: Outflow velocity $m = 1.77$ mg/sec, $t = 4.5$ sec/drop ($h_{Hg} = 40$ cm) at -0.2 V vs. S.C.E.

Results and Discussion

A plot of i_d vs $(h_{eff})^{1/2}$ yielded a straight line showing the diffusion controlled nature of the waves. The plots of $\log \frac{(i_d - i)}{i}$ vs. $-E_{d.e.}$ were also linear,

whose slopes (0.06 ± 0.02) were agreeing with the theoretical value of one electron transfer process, indicating the reversibility of the electrode reaction. The values of i_d and $-E_{1/2}$ for different ligand concentration (C_x) are mentioned in Table 1.

With increase in C_x , the shift in $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative potential and decrease in i_d were observed, indicating the complex formation between Tl⁺ and RSH. The curvature obtained in the plot of $-E_{1/2}$

TABLE I— $E_{1/2}$, i_d AND α_j VALUES AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATION OF RSH

Conc. of ligand (moles/liter)	$i_d(\mu A)$		$-E_{1/2}$ volts		α_j values at 25°		
	25°	35°	25°	35°	α_0	α_1	α_2
0.00	4.10	4.80	0.4620	0.4020	—	—	—
0.02	3.80	4.50	0.4650	0.4650	0.8214	0.1544	0.0246
0.04	3.60	4.30	0.4690	0.4685	0.6683	0.2513	0.0802
0.06	3.50	4.20	0.4730	0.4730	0.5558	0.3134	0.1501
0.08	3.45	4.10	0.4780	0.4780	0.4507	0.3389	0.2164
0.10	3.40	4.00	0.4830	0.4825	0.3656	0.3436	0.2742
0.12	3.40	4.00	0.4870	0.4875	0.3123	0.3526	0.3377

A manual polarograph in conjunction with a thermostated H-cell was used for recording the

vs. $-\log C_x$, showed the formation of successive complexes (Fig. 1).

 Fig. 1. Plot of $-E_{1/2}$ vs. $-\log C_x$ at 25° .

Calculation of overall stability constants

According to DeFord and Hume's method⁹

$$F_0(X) = \text{antilog} \left\{ 0.435 \frac{nF}{RT} \left[(E^0_{1/2})_s - (E^0_{1/2})_c \right] + \log \frac{I_s}{I_c} \right\} \quad \dots (1)$$

Here the sign and meaning, of the terms are the same as those in¹⁰, which became conventional. On the other hand the complexity function $F_j(X)$ is defined as:

$$F_j(X) = 1 + \beta_1(X) + \beta_2(X)^2 + \dots + \beta_n(X)^n + \dots + \beta_N(X)^N \quad \dots (2)$$

where (X) is the ligand concentration, n is the number of ligand molecules; ($0 \leq n \leq N$), N is the coordination number of the complex forming metal (M) and β_n is the overall stability constant of the complex MX_n . From the experimental data, the complexity function $F_j(X)$ [Fig. 2] which is polynomial in (X) , is set up; the coefficients of the latter are required, β_n . Graphical extrapolation reduces the polynomial equation (2) to N -equations from which the corresponding β_n are obtained and are given below:

Composition of complex	Stability constants	
	25°	35°
1 : 1	9.4	8.4
1 : 2	75.0	67.5

From known stability constant data, values of the degree of formation (Fig. 3, Table 1), for each complex in a system have been calculated from following equation¹¹ at 25° .

$$\alpha_j = \frac{\beta_j(X)^j}{F_0(X)}$$

Thermodynamic functions. The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS for complexation are determined at 35° by

 Fig. 2. Values of $F_0(X)$, $F_1(X)$ and $F_2(X)$ for Tl^{+1} in 2-mercapto-ethanol media at 25° .

 Fig. 3. Distribution of complex species as a function of ligand concentration in the thallium-2-mercapto-ethanol system at 25° .

employing the standard equations⁶, and are as follows:

Composition of complex	ΔG (K.cal/mole)	ΔH (K.cal/mole)	ΔS (Cal/degree/mole)
1 : 1	-1.30	-2.05	-2.42
1 : 2	-2.57	-1.92	+2.12

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